

Objects of Resistance and Expression: Rethinking the Concept of ‘Kitsch’ in the Everyday life of the Modern Individual

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Abstract

There are objects which “break” the norms of the pseudo-products of the culture industry that could be said to be without any spirit. In this respect, the family of the kitsch objects (with a notion of play) and the kind of objects that Lukas (1997) defines as “inconspicuous consumption” become more and more attractive to the metropolitan city-dwellers who experience the “loveless disregard to things (Adorno 1997, 41).”

The ways in which the kitsch object could be evaluated as an item of festivity and an arena of subjectivity for the modern individual is the basic discussion. In order to escape the boredom or the routine of everyday life, there should be a break. The kitsch object enables this break to happen through playfulness, resemblance and motion. They open up a space in the boredom of everyday; a space similar to the function of funfair: a mechanical replica of the living things.

Everyday, the city dwellers while walking on the street pass through the small funfairs created by the objects of festivity. The atmosphere suggested by those objects, do create a break (paradoxically the break also helps to ensure the routine and enables the cycle to continue), a sense of stopping of time and reference to space, that are resulted by the fascination for the mechanical wisdom and loud theatricality demonstrated by those artifacts. This ‘play’ notion that kitsch objects offer can be analyzed as part of the emotion-driven design.

Keywords: Everyday Life, Modernity, Design, Identity, Kitsch, Festivity

The Category of “Kitsch” objects

No matter how much we scorn it, kitsch is an integral part of the human condition.
(Kundera 1985)

If the idea of “consumerism being the motor of modernity” is accepted then design should be admitted as a very significant element of industrial production. If design supplies the rational separation of form and function, then there would always be irrational applications through the system of production, because it depends on profit and design increases the expenses. So, in terms of modernity, there rises the concept of “kitsch.” The point that will be stated in the case of kitsch depends on the irrational (in the sense that there is not a direct, rational relation between the form, function and the meaning of a particular object), but on the other hand what I would like to call ‘spontaneous’ production of objects as commodities. This

spontaneity is much more related to being the result of the dynamic of the system than it is a part of.

Modernity and kitsch—the notions might seem mutually exclusive, at least insofar as modernity implies antitraditional presentness, experiment, newness of Pound's "Make it New," commitment to change, while kitsch—for all its diversity—suggests repetition, banality, triteness. But in fact it is difficult to realize that kitsch, technologically as well as aesthetically, is one of the products of modernity....one may take the presence of kitsch in countries of the "Second" or "Third" world as an unmistakable sign of "modernization" (Calinescu 1987, 226).

As Calinescu states: "...the whole concept of kitsch clearly centers around such questions as imitation, forgery, counterfeit and what we may call the aesthetics of deception and self-deception (1987, 229)."

What kitsch is faking could be found in Greenberg's analysis. He says with the industrial revolution and urbanization;

...the peasants who settled in the cities as proletariat and petty bourgeois... but they did not win the leisure and comfort necessary for the enjoyment of the city's traditional culture. Losing, nevertheless, their taste for the folk culture whose background was the countryside, and discovering a new capacity for boredom at the same time, the new urban masses set up a pressure on society to provide them with a kind of culture fit for their own consumption. To fill the demand of the new market a new commodity was devised: ersatz culture, kitsch destined for those who, insensible to the values of genuine culture, are hungry nevertheless for the diversion that only culture of some sort can provide (Greenberg 1967, 153).

Greenberg's statement provides us with important keywords such as; city's traditional culture; folk culture; urban masses; boredom; new market; new commodity; ersatz culture; genuine culture. Among them 'boredom' will be elaborated in further discussions with its essential relation with the phenomenon of kitsch. But still, the dualities of real-fake; low culture-high culture; the countryside-the city implies that kitsch is a category arising from controversies or immanent contradictions. Where design could be seen as the immaculate ideal of modernity, kitsch is the damned child of it. The more the fakeness of kitsch is to be made-believe, the more the truth it seems to be concealing is sustained and in a sense overvalued under the generic names of tradition or origin.

The links between lying and kitsch are too close. Similarly, “a sign is everything which can be taken as significantly substituting for something else. This something else does not necessarily have to exist or to actually be somewhere at the moment in which a sign stands in for it.... If something can not be used to tell a lie, conversely it can not be used to tell the truth: it can not in fact be used ‘to tell’ at all (Eco 1976, 7).” Olalquiaga puts forward this relationship of kitsch with signification beautifully and may be a bit sadly in her essay: “The Pandemoniac Junk Shop of Solitude: Kitsch and Death.”

Kitsch begins in emptiness: a hollow, suspended silence extending without horizons suddenly occupied by an implacable rush of images....

“Deathjoy in repetition.” Kitsch compulsively accumulates signs until it produces an overkill of signification, covering every surface, invoking all possible textures....

Fragmentary, kitsch creates metonymic associations, using parts instead of wholes, establishing meaning by syntagmatic continuity instead of paradigmatic reference (Olalquiaga 1993, 164).

First of all it should be noted that every object could be read as a sign if there is such a reception. Secondly kitsch objects can be read as signs, because they already use the common codes shared by the society, such as common codes of certain styles or periods. The producers of kitsch act generously in using and applying all the different codes on top of each other on the same object without looking whether they are synthesized or integrated. So it is a free arena to play with meaning, connotation and surplus values. The manner of the production is done in such a short and clear-cut way that it goes beyond being sharp, it turns out to be the free medium of cut and paste. The kitsch object becomes a collage of meaning and signification. In such a play with objectual symbolism, the issue can be interpreted as the cultural unconscious coming out to the surface through material production.

An analysis of the artefact must begin with its most obvious characteristic, which is that it exists as a physically concrete form independent of any individual’s mental image of it. This factor may provide the key to understanding its power and significance in cultural construction. The importance of this physicality of the artefact derives from its ability thereby to act as a bridge, not only between the mental and the physical worlds, but also, quite unexpectedly, between consciousness and unconscious (Miller 1987, 99).

Miller's conception of the consciousness and the unconscious is slightly different from Lacan's understanding of the relationship between language and the unconscious. He says "...as language strengthens its hold on consciousness and, through writing, on the explicit world of knowledge, objects may retain their place in the ordering of the unconscious world (Miller 1987, 99)." He means that in the stage of passing to the realm of the symbolic world of language, objects play an important role, acting as a bridge between the world and its mental image of it. By being physical and concrete, unlike language they become the agents of the ordering of the unconscious. This carries the discussion into a quite problematic circle. As theoretically inseparable categories, this argument forces us to differentiate between the signifier and the mental image of it, as belonging to the conscious or the unconscious. This is a very difficult, may be an impossible task to accomplish. It could be tied to the visibility of the signifier, in this case, the object as a visual image, like any other image belonging to the imaginary. Objects provide a linguistic capacity of signification, that is clear, but nevertheless a question resides whether they borrow this capacity from language itself or not. Going back to the Lacanian conception, it can be argued that language enables us to use objects as part of any signification activity. Miller's point is that there are "...qualities of the object that language cannot share (1987, 98)."

This phenomenon can be summarized as the relation between form and its meaning. If there are certain qualities of the object that language can not share, then it arises from the discrepancies or the impossibility of the reciprocity of a form and its meaning. That is why objects can or should be studied, because they stand at the threshold of the signifier and signified; of form and the meaning; of the physical and the abstract; of the conscious and the unconscious. As a free arena of signifiers, it would make things easier to study objects of kitsch, to demonstrate the interrelations between the formerly counted dualities.

There could be various axis of inquiry in studying kitsch. As being a very problematic category, both covering the cheap and the most expensive artifacts; from the most trivial to the essential, kitsch defines a wide range of objects. For example display, and the desire for upward mobility is also immanent to kitsch, because it copies whatever is already valuable, so the displayer of the item speaks of this desire through his/her choices. This is the first advantage of the kitsch object. It allows the user on a metonymical level, an easy way to express himself. This is not to say that other objects do not provide this kind of capacity. The convenience of kitsch derives from its vulgar use of resemblance.

Figure 1, Soap dispenser

An example would be illuminating at this point to build up the links specifically among unconscious, kitsch and identity. The example chosen is a plastic soap dispenser (Figure 1). In fact its name is “De Luxe Woman Hand Soap Dish,” and is produced by *Burcak Plastik A.S.* As written on the cover the design is registered. The object is like a woman’s hand that is holding the soap without actually touching it. There is a magnet underneath and a round metal piece embedded in the soap is attracted by the magnet, so that the soap seems to be magically floating under the elegant hand of the lady. The long red nails and the ring which is an accessory of beauty reinforce the gender message of the object. So this object, with its intense gender encoding could be said to be matching the gender categories of the user of this specific product within the level of unconscious. As a cheap, plastic object, this soap dish might be said to target lower income families, as potential consumers.

The object opens up a fantasy space by demanding an active reciprocity between itself and the user. This is a gestural reciprocity. The object pretends to give a hand and the user have to respond in order to take the soap. The magical floating increases the effect of the fantastic or even erotic atmosphere created by the object. Another function of the floating is to provide the untouchableness of the hand. The object cause of desire can not be attained, as it should be, to be able to remain as an object of desire. The product is like an actress on stage and a quite successful one playing with the notions of desire and gender. It is a mass produced and design registered fantasy object with the adhesive tube included in the package made to be hung on the metal rods in quantities in the market.

Everyday life, play and objects

Implying that the domain of kitsch objects have a potential in being points of resistance and self-expression then a question can be asked if the kitsch object is a way out of the system of the culture industry as being a “spontaneous” cultural production; or is this one of the

dynamics of the system itself creating the illusion that it can be altered? The question brings various other ones such as if it would be relevant to argue that the culture industry or any other mechanism of the market economy depending on creating and selling difference is not fully successful in doing so. May be people are more standardized than they were before, but may be they are not as much as intended. Similarly, it becomes more difficult to reduce cultural production as well as consumption easily to a servant of the same system. There are objects which “break” the norms of the pseudo-product which is without any spirit. So the family of the kitsch objects (with a notion of play) and the kind of objects that Lukas (1997) defines as “inconspicuous consumption” become more and more attractive to the metropolitan city-dwellers who experience the “loveless disregard to things (Adorno 1997, 41).”

There could be various responses. Firstly, following De Certeau (1984), these objects and the users of them could be argued to act their ‘tactics’ over the ‘designed’ products that carry the codes of ‘being designed.’ The kitsch object could be seen as a reaction to the dominant system of objects with all the plasticity and non-durability as being their common character. These characteristics can also be shared by the family of kitsch objects as well. What else then does kitsch offer as a personal space for the consumer as the subject who chooses?

At this point, an introduction of a new concept will be helpful complementary to the everyday life theory put forward formerly by Lefebvre. It is the concept of ‘festival.’ As Asa Berger explains the significance of festival in relation or within everyday life:

EVERYDAY LIFE	FESTIVAL
Routine	Special
work	leisure, play, holidays
boredom	Excitement
uniformity	Difference
continual	Sporadic
travel	Tourism

Table 1, Comparison of everyday life and festival

Everyday life is the realm of the routine, whereas Festival represents an interruption of this routine in the name of celebration and excitement. In everyday life we spend most of our time at work, while Festival, in its modern manifestations, is devoted to leisure, play and fun. Festival opposes the excitement of special moments (whether during something like Carnival in Rio or New Orleans) to the relatively boring and unexciting aspects of everyday life.

.....
In the modern world, leisure has lost its festivity and has been absorbed, so to speak, by our consumer culture; leisure has become what Lefebvre calls “a generalized display: television, cinema, tourism” (Asa Berger 1996, 24-25).

Then how could the kitsch object be evaluated as an item of festivity and an arena of subjectivity for the modern individual? In order to escape the boredom or the routine of everyday life, there should be a break. The kitsch object enables this break to happen through playfulness, resemblance and motion. The referred set of objects is a specific group. Not all kitsch can supply these. The kind of objects that have been the subject of this analysis generally can be gathered under the name of ‘designed kitsch.’ Examples could be seen in the Figures 2, 3, 4. The three designs do have certain common characteristics that are they all are made of plastics and designed to fulfill a specific function. The crucial point here is that, the way they are made to fulfill that specific function is in accordance with the associated kind of motion from the animal that is taken as the model. Under the beak of the pelican, a fluorescent light bulb is placed, and when you raise the beak it becomes a table light. Similarly, the orange frog opens its mouth to get the trash in. And the bird leans forward as if eating seeds, but this time takes the tooth pick from the container and waits readily for you to take it from its beak, like a well dressed waiter. The good use of color for all of the three designs has enhanced their formal resemblance that they were intended to achieve. On the other hand, the transformation of the motion to the object could be said to have an indexical tone that is successful both in providing a match with the animal’s motion and the object’s; but also the reference points for the motion is perceivable and emphasized through the object language. Although they can be called kitsch, they are well-designed. Is this a paradox? That could be another question, but their most important characteristic is that they open up a space in the boredom of everyday, a space similar to the function of funfair; a mechanical replica of the living things. The form-function duality here gains another meaning that is formally, i.e.; when they are not working they do not reveal their functions. It is not the case in for anonymous objects, like a regular piece of scissors, or a wooden spoon. The form and

function are in a sense united in those. Here, even when the light is on, the lamp pretends to be a pretty pelican.

Although they are toy-like, they still need their users, or wait to be used unlike the noisy, cheerful and self-operating relatives that demonstrate their one-man shows on the streets. For example, the soldier crawling on the ground with his rifle and shooting regularly; or the seal turning on his nose constantly with the colorful ball attached to it, or the self-operating toy cars moving, twisting and tumbling around in small cardboard boxes (Figure 5).

Figure 2, Toothpick container

Figure 3, Table lamp

Figure 4, Trash bin

Figure 5, Self-operating car

Everyday, the city dwellers while walking on the street, going to their work or going home pass through the small funfairs created by the objects of festivity. Either we buy them or not, the atmosphere suggested by those objects, do create a break (paradoxically the break also helps to ensure the routine and enables the cycle to continue), a sense of stopping of time and reference to space, that are resulted by the fascination for the mechanical wisdom and loud theatricality demonstrated by those artifacts.

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